

Determination of Sodium Carboxylates by Reaction with *o*-Bromoacetophenone

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Manuscript received 11 May 1981, accepted 14 August 1981

CARBOXYLATES can be acidimetrically titrated with hydrochloric and perchloric acids¹, using either visual or potentiometric indication. The silver salt method² does not hold reliability, primarily due to the sensitivity of the silver salts towards light and air and secondly due to the non-stoichiometric composition of the salts obtained from the aromatic acids containing two nitro groups. The combustion approach³ for determining metal carboxylates involving the oxidation of the sample to the corresponding carbonate followed by determination of the latter is quite time consuming.

A titrimetric procedure for the determination of carboxylates based on quantitative reaction with *o*-bromoacetophenone, has been developed. A sodium carboxylate is reacted with *o*-bromoacetophenone in acetonitrile-water medium, the excess of the latter being determinable by reaction with thiourea resulting in the formation of 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole hydrobromide⁴, titratable^{5,6} with alkali, using phenolphthalein as indicator. Though tested with a selection of sodium carboxylates, the procedure seems to hold general applicability. The accuracy of the procedure is evident from the standard deviations of the results. The procedure, therefore, merits recommendation.

Experimental

A weighed quantity (0.2-1.0 mmole) of a sodium carboxylate and *o*-bromoacetophenone, in

two-fold excess, are dissolved in 12 ml of acetonitrile-water (10 : 2). The solution is refluxed for the required period of time as recorded in Table 1 followed by the addition of excess of

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF SODIUM CARBOXYLATES

Carboxylate*	Recovery Average %	Reaction period (min)	Standard deviation
Acetate (4)	99.83	30	0.08
<i>n</i> -Propionate (3)	100.00	45	0.02
<i>n</i> -Butyrate (4)	99.98	45	0.06
Benzoate (4)	99.95	30	0.08
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzoate (4)	99.99	30	0.08
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzoate (4)	99.92	30	0.08
<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoate (3)	99.77	45	0.28
3,5-Dinitrobenzoate (4)	99.96	30	0.06
Phenylacetate (4)	99.91	30	0.07
Phenoxyacetate (4)	99.81	30	0.17

* Figures in parentheses represent number of determinations.

thiourea at room temperature (25°). The solution is allowed to stand for 10 min and 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole hydrobromide, thus formed, is titrated against 0.1 *M* sodium hydroxide, using phenolphthalein (3 drops, 0.5% solution in ethanol) as indicator to a light pink colouration holding stability for a min.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. M. M. Bokadia for laboratory facilities and to C. S. I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Research Fellowship to (S. M.).

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